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**THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THEORETICAL EDUCATION AND PRACTICAL ACTIVITY
IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL QUALITIES OF FUTURE SPECIALISTS**

<https://zenodo.org/records/17842170>

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Abstract. *This article discusses the problem of increasing the efficiency of the educational process through the use of practice-oriented methods in the organization of education in order to develop professional readiness.*

Keywords: *professional readiness, competence, improving of readiness, practice-oriented teaching, innovative approach to education.*

Annotatsiya. *Maqolada talabalarning kasbiy tayyorgarligini rivojlantirish maqsadida ta'limni tashkil etishda amaliy faoliyatga yo'naltirilgan usullaridan foydalanish orqali ta'lim jarayonini samaradorligini oshirish masalasi yoritilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *kasbiy tayyorgarlik, kompetentlik, tayyorgarlikni rivojlantirish, amaliy faoliyatga yo'naltirilgan ta'lim, ta'limda innovatsion yondashuv.*

Аннотация. *В статье рассматривается проблема повышения эффективности образовательного процесса за счет использования практико-ориентированных методов в организации образования с целью развития профессиональной готовности студентов.*

Ключевые слова: *профессиональная готовность, компетентность, развитие готовности, практико-ориентированное обучение, инновационный подход в образовании.*

The theoretical knowledge gained by students in the educational process will undoubtedly become the basis of their professional skills. But at the same time, not only the knowledge of future teachers is important, but also the level of professional readiness. Confirmation of this can also be seen in the results of a number of recent studies conducted by local and foreign scientists.

In addition, as evidence of our opinion, we can cite the work of some researchers: T.M. Bakikhina studied this issue and came to the conclusion that "Professional competence is the degree of a formed system of knowledge, skills, abilities, and individual initiatives necessary for effective implementation specific activity" [1, 26]. The difference between competence and knowledge lies not only in knowledge about the activity, but also in its manifestation, the difference between competence and skill is that it can be applied to questions of different content. "The development of competence is assessed, first of all, by the end result (managed - failed to complete the task)" [2, 133], which allows a person to act not only in their usual conditions, but also in new, non-standard conditions.

Some researchers believe that the concepts of "competence" and "competence" are synonyms that mean the same concepts. Regarding this issue, we agree with I.P. Medintseva, she explains these terms as follows: "competence (a set of interrelated personality traits set in relation to a certain range of objects and processes) and competence (possession, possession of a person of the appropriate competence, including his personal attitude to her and the subject of activity) " [3].

Thus, we define competence as "the subject's ability to work with objects of activity or the subject's ability to effectively use previously acquired knowledge and skills in a particular

situation, the ability to successfully carry out professional activities” and we decided to look at “competence” as an indicator of a future teacher's training.

However, this decision clarifies the problem of insufficient participation of students in practical activities in the educational process, which in some cases does not have sufficient opportunities for practical activities.

Despite the large number of scientific studies carried out by scientists on the relationship between science, education and industry, in universities in real life, technoparks, various subsidiary enterprises and manufacturing enterprises are insufficiently formed. This in turn leads to the assessment of practical skills again in the classroom - in a theoretical process.

It is clear that we will not be able to achieve the intended goal if we do not ensure continuity between production (which enables practical activity), which forms practical skills and education, which ensures the intellectual growth of the participant in the process. The reason is that knowledge is a product of intellectual activity, while training, on the contrary, manifests itself in practical activity. As a conclusion, we can say that it is necessary to develop a mechanism for determining the level of readiness of future personnel, their ability to fully meet the requirements of the employer, to develop a mechanism for testing the skills to perform professional activities at a high level.

Another aspect of the problem is the fact that pedagogical practice, which is the practical activity of the future teacher, is carried out at the end of the educational process and excludes the possibility of research or correction of any mistakes or omissions during practice.

As a solution to this problem, we recommend improving the learning environment by expanding its scope.

That is, in the learning process, students have the opportunity to spend their free time as a volunteer, trainee and intern (at industrial enterprises) to gain experience in their chosen field. This approach not only makes it possible to link the formal form of education with non-formal forms, but also allows young professionals to demonstrate their abilities in front of potential employers and further continue their professional career after training.

However, it is becoming more and more obvious that in modern conditions, at a time when existing technologies and knowledge are rapidly updated and improved, it is impossible to train highly qualified personnel while staying inside the building of educational institutions. And yet, it should be noted that in order for the current education system to adapt to new requirements and serve as the basis for the formation of students' skills that meet the requirements of modern society, it should be borne in mind that applicants cannot always consciously choose the path of their future career and feel the need for its further improvement.

In many cases, the basic requirements of the employer begin with the work experience of the personnel. A serious requirement for the training of a future teacher in such conditions is not only the formation of knowledge and skills, but also the development of important professional qualities, the ability to seek and implement new approaches to education and upbringing. The reality is that university graduates are not sufficiently prepared to organize their professional activities. Therefore, it is necessary to think about the process of developing the professional competence of the future teacher, which is an indicator of his professional pedagogical training.

In the process of studying the problems of students' readiness, a number of reasons were identified that hinder their preparation at a high level. The experiment revealed that the main reasons for the relatively low level of training of students are: 1) partial inconsistency between

the materials presented in the topic and with current situations; 2) problem situations – are not sufficiently relevant and their abstract nature, as well as separation from real life; 3) lack of motivation for education among students; 4) the prevalence of non-practical forms of education; 5) insufficient attention is paid to the organization of practical activities and independent work of students in the educational process. [4, 8]

To solve these problems, we need to do the following: First: focus on the form of learning. It must be borne in mind that the content of education can be mastered only in the process of active activity of the subject, and organize the educational process on the basis of practice-oriented technologies. Secondly: the study of the content of the subject requires taking into account the presence of objects of research. To achieve this goal, great attention should be paid to practical developmental methods, such as practice-oriented interactive methods, problem situations, cases and much more. Third: content is related to teaching methods. In didactics, several forms of its presentation have been developed, each of which determines a specific program of educational and cognitive activity: verbal-descriptive, structural-conceptual, system-activity, and others. The latter plays a priority role in the organization of the educational process.

Such a system can teach students to form their roadmap for the consciously and independently (by themselves) development of their professional development, even in the early stages of learning.

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MURAKKAB EFIRLAR MAVZUSINI O'QITISHDA DEMONSTRATSION TAJRIBALARDAN FOYDALANISH METODIKASI

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Annotatsiya. *Murakkab efirlarni o'qitishda keltirilgan zamonaviy metodlar va shakllardan samarali foydalanish o'quvchilarning mavzuni yaxshi o'zlashtirishiga, ularning kimyo faniga qiziqishini oshirishga va amaliy ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga yordam beradi. O'qituvchi esa o'quvchilarning*

